
ASSESSMENT OF RIVER BED EROSION AND MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES GENERATED FROM STEADIED DREDGING SHIPS IN HARBOUR ZONES

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Abstract: *Assessment of river bed erosion and morphological changes creates a better understanding of the specific characteristics and processes in a water body, vital in generating an implementable effective watershed management strategies. In this work, erosion pins were deployed in studying the river bed erosion and changes in the bed morphology within and off the harbour to study bed erosion prior steadied and no steadied dredging ship activities. Thus, measurements and variations were used to quantify the river bed erosion due to steadied ships. The bed morphology was also assessed prior physical change. From results obtained, it was found that steadied ship at harbours contribute to bed erosion of the study area at rate of 2.7cmhr⁻¹.*

Keywords: Soil Erosion; Water Erosion; Geological Erosion; Accelerated Erosion; Water Erosion Types; Bed Erosion; Dredging; etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

The world population is on the increase even with a declining growth rate (Okolotu and Oluka 2021a; Okolotu *et al.*, 2024). Securing and conserving coastal environment against erosion is vital for land availability, agricultural and other beneficial purposes. Erosion of river results from geomorphic processes controlled by interactions between natural mechanism and environmental stress factors (Henshaw *et al.* 2013; Chassiot *et al.* 2020) at present enhanced by human pressure (Best 2019; Goudie 2020; Piegay *et al.* 2020; Wohl 2020). Human activities add several stressors to river geo – ecosystems, such as ship traffic (Scarpa *et al.* 2019; Bernier *et al.* 2021). Currently, a high percentage of the decision making process for river erosion management is based on economic considerations (Rangel – Buitrago and Anfuso 2015), local non – integrated approaches to develop solutions (Rangel – Buitrago *et al.* 2018) and fears of the stakeholders (Finkl 2016) (Bernier *et al.* 2021). There are six main erosion processes, which are often interconnected: gravity, wind, rain, rivers, oceans, glaciers (BGS, 2024). Erosion is divided into soil and water erosion. Individually, soil erosion and water erosion are further divided using different criterias. These are outline below;

I. Soil Erosion: Soil erosion is the detachment and transportation of soil materials from one place to another through the action of wind, water in motion or by beating action of rain. The most common agent of soil erosion in Nigeria is water. Wind erosion is a more serious problem for agricultural lands in the arid and semiarid regions of the world (*e.g.*, North Africa, the Near East, parts of Asia, Australia, northwest China, southern South America, and North America) (Porazinska and Wall, 2001). Soil erosion process is classified as geologic erosion (by natural process) and accelerated erosion (erosion by human activities) (Okolotu and Oluka, 2021). These two main types of erosion: geological and accelerated erosion are further explained below;

i. Geological Erosion: This is a normal process of weathering that generally occurs at low rates in all soil as part of the natural soil forming processes. Erosion is a geological process in which earthen materials (*i.e.*, soil, rocks, sediments) are worn away and transported over time by natural forces such as water or wind (Mulvihill, 2021). It occurs over a long geological time horizons and is not influenced by human activity. The wearing away of rocks and formation of soil profiles are processes affected by the slow but continuous geological erosion.

ii. Accelerated Erosion: This is due to artificial cause or sets of man and is as old as agriculture. It is called “accelerated” because it speeds up the geologic soil erosion; thus upsetting the balance between soil forming processes and soil loss (Okolotu and Oluka, 2021). Soil erosion becomes a major concern when rate of erosion exceeds a certain threshold level and become rapid. This type of erosion is triggered by anthropogenic causes like deforestation, slash and burn agriculture, intensive plowing, intensive and controlled grazing and biomass burning. Identifying where and when accelerated erosion occurs is a critical first step toward its effective management. (Webb *et al.*, 2014). Accelerated soil erosion causes adverse agronomic, ecological, environmental and economic effects on both on-site and off-site. Apart from agricultural lands, quality of the forest, pastures, and range lands are affected. The on-site consequence involves primarily the reduction in soil productivity while the off-site consequences are mostly due to the sediment and chemicals transported away from the source into natural waters by streams. Also soil erosion reduce soil fertility, alter water quality and increases risk in global change and food insecurity.

II. Water Erosion: This is the wearing away of soil surfaces by water from rain, runoff, snowmelt, and irrigation. Soil erosion by water occurs when bare-sloped soil surface is exposed to rainfall, and the rainfall intensity exceeds the rate of soil intake, or infiltration rate, leading to soil-surface runoff (LSUEO, 2024). Water is estimated to be responsible for more than one-half the global soil degradation, followed by wind, chemical (*e.g.*, salinization, acidification, pollutants, atmospheric nitrogen deposition, excessive fertilizers, pesticides and manures), and physical (soil compaction, water logging, subsidence) degradation (Porazinska and Wall, 2001). This refers to the movement of soil organic and inorganic particles along the soil surface with the flowing water and deposition of

eroded materials at lower landscape positions and in aquatic ecosystems. Types of water erosion include: splash erosion, inter-rill erosion, rill erosion, gully erosion, stream-banks erosion, *etc.*

i. Splash Erosion: Raindrops impacts on the soil surface disperse and splash the soil, thereby displacing particles from their original position. Splash erosion is caused by the bombardment of soil surfaces by impacting raindrops. Studies in America have shown that splashed particles may rise as high as 0.6 metres above the ground and move up to 1.5 metres horizontally (DNRET, 2014). Processes of splash erosion involve raindrop impact, splash of soil particles followed by the formation of craters. Splash erosion or raindrop impact represents the first stage in the erosion process (DNRET, 2014).

ii. Inter-Rill Erosion: As rain starts, runoff develops diminutive rills and that portion of runoff that flows between rills is called inter-rill erosion. This is mostly due to shallow flow. Inter-rill erosion is the most common type of water erosion. Splash and inter-rill erosion make up about 70% of total soil erosion. They occur simultaneously although splash erosion dominates during initial process.

iii. Rill Erosion: This refers to soil erosion that occurs in small channels or rills. This occurs due to concentrated flow rather than shallow flow. Rill erosion occurs during heavy rains, when small rills form over an entire hillside, making farming difficult (LSUEO, 2024). Rill erosion is the second most common pathway of soil erosion. It comprises numerous small channels of less than 30cm depth (DPIRD, 2023). Runoff water that concentrates in small channels erodes soil at faster rates than inter-rill erosion, and as the force of flow and the soil particles creeping along the rill bed enlarge rill.

iv. Gully Erosion: Gully erosion are either v or u shaped channels. Gullies are linear incisor channels of at least 0.3m width and 0.3m depth. Gullies are deep (>30cm), open, incised and unstable channels, sufficiently large to disrupt normal farming operations (DPIRD, 2023). They are primarily formed by concentrated runoff converging in lower point of the field. The two types of gullies are; Ephemeral gullies (Shallow channels that can be readily corrected by routine tillage operations) and permanent gullies (Too large to be smoothed by regular tillage and require expensive measures of reclamation and control). Gully erosion makes gullies, some of them huge, impossible to cross with farm machinery (LSUEO, 2024).

v. Sheet Erosion: Sheet erosion is the uniform removal of soil in thin layers, and it occurs when soil particles are carried evenly over the soil surface by rainwater that does not infiltrate into the ground (HPM, 2019). Sheet erosion often appears as small sediment deposits behind tufts of grass (DPIRD, 2023).

vi. Stream-Banks Erosion: The collapsing of banks along streams, creeks, and rivers due to erosive power of runoff from up-lash field pedestals with fresh vertical cut along streams are the results of stream-banks erosion. Planting grasses (example native and tall grass species) and trees, establishing engineering structures (examples tiles, gabions), mulching stream borders with rocks and

woody materials, geo-textile fencing and intercepting/diverting runoff are measures to control stream-banks erosion.

Figure 1: Rills and gullies formed by concentrated water flowing over a slope (NYSG, 2015).

The effects of water erosion include: loss of productive soil, deposition of sand on productive field, fragmentation of levels, silting of reservoirs, silting of drainage and irrigation channels, *etc.*

i. Loss Of Productive Soil: This is one of the most severe problems of erosion. The surface soil loss with runoff water consists of rich productive soil and fresh organic matter, and when carried away, hampers agricultural productivity.

ii. Deposition Of Sand On Productive Field: Usually, plane fertile lands have been made unproductive by the deposition of coarse materials brought down from the hills by streams, rivers and other agents of erosion.

iii. Fragmentation Of Levels: Gully erosion in an area may end up dividing the farm or field into many valleys and ridges thus making it fragmented. Crop rolls are shortened, movement from field is obstructed and farm value is decreased. Construction works like roads, bridges, building and fences are often damaged by gully development.

iv. Silting Of Reservoirs: Water erosion in a catchment area of reservoirs results in deposition of soil thus reducing their storage capacity and shortening their useful life.

v. Silting Of Drainage And Irrigation Channels: Also, deposition of silt in drainage ditches, streams and rivers reduces their depth and capacity to handle runoff. As a result, overflow and flooding of downstream area increases with damage of crops and disaster to man-made structures.

III. Bed Erosion: Bed erosion is the wearing of soil within the bed or bottom of water bodies. The eroded sediment poses various problems in the river ecosystem including river bank failure (Wuppukondur and Chandra, 2017). The four main types of bed erosion processes include; Hydraulic

action (The shear power of the water as it smashes against the river bed and banks), Abrasion (When pebbles grind along the river bank and bed with a scratching impact), Attrition (When river water knock rocks against each other to break apart, forming smaller and more erodible particles), Solution (When the water dissolves certain types of rocks, like limestone to smaller erodible particle sizes).

IV. Dredging: Dredging is the removal of sediments and debris from the bottom of lakes, rivers, harbors, and other water bodies (NOAA, 2024). These are ships primarily designed and built for soil harnessing from the water bodies. It is the process of unearthing aquatic beds by dragging to bring them to the surface using dredgers (Okolotu and Oluka, 2021). These harnessed soils are used for many economical purposes like civil and construction works like buildings. Soils of different types are harnessed including sands, silts, gravels, granites, *etc.* A typical dredging ship obtains sands from the offshore and through pumping, dispatches it on the coast where it is collected by trucks and distributed at commercial prices. The three main types of dredgers include: Trailing Suction Hopper Dredger, TSHD (This is mainly used for dredging loose and soft soil such as sand, gravel, silt or clay), Backhoe Dredger, BHD (This is basically a pontoon equipped with a hydraulic excavator which excavate the soil, and discharge it into the hopper barge that is moored alongside the pontoon), Cutter Suction Dredger, CSD (This is equipped with rotating cutter head, for cutting and fragmenting hard soils (Okolotu and Oluka, 2021).Dredging is also performed to reduce the exposure of fish, wildlife, and people to contaminants and to prevent the spread of contaminants to other areas of the water body (NOAA, 2024). The dredged material can vary greatly (peat and organic soils, cobbles, clays, boulders, silts, broken rock, sands, rock and gravels, cemented soils and corals), and dredging depth can vary from a few meters to more than a hundred meters (Notteboom, 2022).A typical example of the dredging ship is presented in figure 2, below;

Figure 2: Steadied Dredging Ships In The Study Area (Photograph At Study Area)

2. MATERIALS

The main material used in the actualization of this work is the study area. The study area is Asaba, in delta state of Nigeria.

Figure 3: Location Of Study Area And Satellite Map showing Asaba And Its Section Of River Niger (Okolotu and Oluka, 2021a).

Other materials include; the dredging ships, engine boat, erosion pins, etc.

3. METHODS

The measurements and variation in bed sediment removal were used to quantify the river bed erosion. Erosion pins were inserted on the river bed of the study area to study bed erosion for two conditions: harbor zones (for steadied ships), and also, fifteen (15) meter distance off harbor zone (for no steadied ship activity). Upon measurement of the erosion pins, initial and final bed levels on three replications within a time spacing of two hours (2 hrs), the average records were used for necessary computation of their bed variance. These were for five (5) site locations. The bed morphology was also compared prior bed property changes.

Table1: Variables Computations

S/ N	Bed Erosion In Natural Condition in cm			Average Bed Erosion In Natural Condition in cm	Bed Erosion Prior Steadied Ships in cm			Average Bed Erosion Prior Steadied Ships in cm	Bed Variation Beds _{SLV} (cm) = Bed _{L(ss)} - Bed _{L(nc)} (cm)
	Repl icate 1	Repl icate 2	Repl icate 3		Re plic ate 1	Re plic ate 2	Re plic ate 3		
1	3.8	2.7	3.0	3.1	4.2	0.8	6.1	3.7	0.6

2	6.2	1.6	2.2	3.3	8.3	6.7	7.1	7.1	3.8
3	3.1	3.4	3.6	3.4	7.1	5.8	7.6	6.8	3.4
4	1.9	3.8	1.3	2.3	5.8	6.3	4.4	5.5	3.2
5	3.7	3.2	3.3	3.4	4.2	7.6	5.3	5.7	2.3
Av.	3.7	2.9	2.7	3.1	5.9	5.4	6.1	5.8	2.7

Table 2: Bed Morphology Computation

S/N	Bed Distance From Shore (m)	Bed Morphology (m) Off Harbour			Bed Morphology (m) At Harbour Zone			Ship Generated Bed Morphology (m)
		Initial Bed (m)	Final bed (m)	Off Harbo ur Scour	Initial Bed (m)	Final bed (m)	Ship Harbo ur Scour	
1	10	-3.6	-4.1	-0.5	-1.2	-2.1	-0.9	-0.4
2	20	-4.1	-4.2	-0.1	-2.3	-2.6	-0.3	-0.2
3	30	-6.8	-7.6	-0.8	-4.1	-4.4	-0.3	0.5
4	40	-6.7	-7.3	-0.6	-4.5	-4.5	0.0	0.0
5	50	-8.4	-9.6	-1.2	-6.2	-6.2	0.0	0.0
Av.	30	-5.9	-6.6	- 0.3	-3.7	-4.0	-0.5	-0.03

4. RESULTS

The results obtained are presented in tables and figures below;

The results Of Bed Erosion and morphology are presented in tables three and four (3 and 4) below;

Table 3: Results Of Bed Erosion And Bed Variation

S/N	Bed Erosion In Natural Condition	Bed Erosion Prior Steadied Ships	Bed Variation
1	3.1	3.7	0.6
2	3.3	7.1	3.8
3	3.4	6.8	3.4
4	2.3	5.5	3.2
5	3.4	5.7	2.3
Av.	3.1	5.8	2.7

Table 4: Bed Morphology

S/N	Bed Distance From Shore (m)	Ship Generated Bed Morphology (m)
1	10	-0.4
2	20	-0.2

3	30	0.5
4	40	0.0
5	50	0.0
Av.	30	-0.03

The Bed Erosion curve for Natural Condition and Steadied Ships, initial and final curve for Off Harbour Bed, and initial and final curve for Harbour Bed are presented in figures four, five and six (4, 5 and 6), below;

Figure 4: Bed Erosion Curve For Natural Condition And Steadied Ships

Figure 5: Off Harbour Bed

Figure 6: Harbour Bed

5. DISCUSSIONS

At depths higher than the erosion pins, the dredger suction tube was used to support the erosion pins during measurements. This was to avoid the erosion pins being pulled away by the drag force of the river current. The downstream erosion of the river bed deposits the eroded sediments in the upstream river bed through sediments transport along with the water current. This phenomenon replenishes the eroding position overtime from its downstream inflow behind.

Bed morphology was based on the physical changes in bed characteristics. This refers to the scour developments altering the physical feature of the river bed.

Upon water recession after peak rainfall season, *i.e.*, recession that occurs during the dry season. Bed morphology associated to the bank floor used to harbour the ship experienced more scour than the non harbour zones. The impact is however negligible to the coastal users. This is because the affected lands would have been less utilized than the economic benefit the coastal harbour zones provide through dredging of valuable soils usable for various economic purposes both within and outside the coastal environment, through commercial trade.

The clayey banks and bed replenishes slower than the other component soil morphological types in the study area. Bedrocks of igneous were also found to be a major morphological product of the river bed as well as bank landforms due to the scours generated from the harbours.

In harbours with water breakers 5 - 10 meters before the zone, it was recorded that, the slowdown of the water current by diversion of the water force contribute to the morphological modification of the water bed.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Based on results obtained, it was concluded that bed erosion generated by dredging ships was 2.7 cmhr⁻¹. It was thus found that steadied ship at harbours contribute to bed erosion of the study area.

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Ship generated bed erosion occurs more at harbours. Also ship generated bed erosion in harbours are influenced by distance from shores/coasts.

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